

THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AS MARKETING TOOL ON SALES PERFORMANCE OF SMEs IN MALAYSIA

Hanifah Maksin^{1*}, Darren Koay Donq Yew², Douglas Soo Hye Chuan³, Hafiz Mohamed Said⁴, Mohd Faizol Musa⁵, Muhamad Raznaufal Mohd Radzi⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Faculty of Business, UNITAR International University, Malaysia

*Corresponding author, hanifahm@unitar.my

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of social media marketing on the sales performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Malaysia. The data were gathered from 308 business owners. The independent variables are brand awareness, engagement, word-of-mouth, content sharing, and conversion, while the dependent variable is sales performance. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the reliability of the variables. Correlation and regression analysis were conducted to determine the relationship between the variables. Brand awareness, engagement and word-of-mouth do not affect sales performance, which does not support hypotheses ($p > 0.05$). On the other hand, content sharing and conversion positively and significantly affect sales performance. The present study has contributed to the existing body of literature by providing insights into the effect of social media marketing on the sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia. This research recommends conducting a subsequent investigation on the obstacles associated with the execution of social media marketing, such as time constraints, limited resources, and lack of expertise.

Keywords: social media marketing, small and medium enterprises, sales performance

INTRODUCTION

Social media marketing (SMM) has emerged as a noteworthy mechanism for enterprises, including those of a smaller scale, to enhance their operational efficacy and augment their reach among a wider demographic (Silvano & Mbogo, 2022). The proliferation and extensive adoption of social media platforms, including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn, have enabled businesses to identify novel channels for engaging with customers, enhancing brand recognition, and stimulating sales (Djakasaputra et al., 2021; Marolt et al., 2022).

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are widely regarded as the fundamental pillar of Malaysia's economy. Despite being associated with restricted resources and limited capital acquisition, they play a crucial role in the economy. The Internet has provided SMEs with a convenient means to utilise pre-existing resources to transition from traditional marketing methods to present-day marketing. According to Global Digital Insights (Digital 2022), Malaysia's internet penetration rate stood at 89.6% of the total population at the start of 2022, and it will continue to grow in the future. Because of this phenomenon, numerous businesses are required to modify their operational strategies (Sufian et al., 2020).

Various research studies have emphasised social media's benefits in facilitating SMEs' expansion. Using social media platforms, consumers can connect directly with new products, services, and brands easily (Bilgin, 2018; Eid et al., 2020). Through the help of social media, SMEs can get consumer feedback to improve their brands (Munir et al., 2021). SMEs would use social media if they perceived it to be cost-effective (Chatterjee & Kumar Kar, 2020; Karaduman, 2013) and easy to use (Chatterjee & Kumar Kar, 2020). Via social media for marketing prospects for comparing selling and buying issues to arrive at the right decision (Keegan & Rowley, 2017). The use of SMM is claimed to have bridged the connection between SMEs and prospective consumers (Silvia, 2019).

Those studies, however, were conducted before covid-19 hit the world. It is essential to investigate whether utilising SMM can influence SMEs' business growth. This study has attempted to investigate if SMM can act as an effective instrument for business growth, focusing on the sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

This study sought to answer the following objectives:

To study the relationship between brand awareness, engagement, word-of-mouth, content sharing, conversion, and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

To examine the significant association between brand awareness, engagement, word-of-mouth, content sharing, conversion, and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction is crucial for long-term success for companies (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018). According to Philip Kotler, "a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment, which resulted from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome against his/her expectations," constitutes customer satisfaction. Kotler utilizes vague words like pleasure and disappointment, yet the definition is evident nonetheless. Customer satisfaction is important in business because maintaining satisfied customers is cheaper than finding new ones (Mohd Farid Shamsudin, 2020).

Many empirical studies on performance outcomes primarily focus on financial performance, such as sales volume (Affandi et al., 2020; Marolt et al., 2022) and sales growth rate (Dolega et al., 2021). Sales performance is defined as the profit generated from collections and is typically evaluated through a comparative analysis of various periods (Silvano & Mbogo, 2022). The primary objective of any business is to achieve a high sales volume, which is determined by the amount of revenue and profit generated (Marolt et al., 2022). In the context of SMEs, it is anticipated that using social media marketing will result in greater sales volume (Sufian et al., 2020).

BRAND AWARENESS

Brand awareness is consumers' familiarity with an organization and services and will directly impact sales rate (Bilgin, 2018). Brand awareness makes and brings back public emotions, consideration, and general apprehension about the brand (Eid et al., 2020); thus, employing diverse marketing techniques can enhance brand recognition, which can have an indirect impact on sales growth or decline (Marolt et al., 2022; Munir et al., 2021). Studies have reported

that social media marketing has shown a higher business performance in the retail industry (Dolega et al., 2021). Social media marketing creates brand awareness, and due to this, this study is intended to examine if brand awareness has a significant relationship to the sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between brand awareness and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

ENGAGEMENT

Yadav & Sabhayat (2021) stated that customers' prior engagement on firms' social media platforms greatly impacts purchase intentions and leads to boosting sales performance. Using attractive and interactive materials in social media can enhance social media engagement (Song et al., 2021). Hence, this study aims to determine whether engagement and sales performance correlate significantly.

H₂: There is a significant relationship between engagement and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

WORD-OF-MOUTH

Word-of-mouth (WOM) can be pointed out when specific personality traits distinguish the source of WOM messages. Thus, business owners have the potential to enhance their sales by implementing strategies that motivate social media users with unique personality traits and attributes to create and share affirmative WOM messages (Silvia, 2019). This study aims to ascertain whether there is a substantial correlation between WOM and sales performance.

H₃: There is a significant relationship between word-of-mouth and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

CONTENT SHARING

Content sharing and sales performance have a relationship and it is an ingenious way to reach potential customers worldwide (Dwivedi et al., 2021). This will help to increase exposure on social media and boost sales performance by improving content sharing on social media platforms, helping firms enhance the efficacy of their marketing campaigns (Peng et al., 2018). The content must be useful, accurate, and trustworthy. This will help bring in customers. Given how important content is, this study tries to find out if sharing good online content will affect the sales performance of SMEs.

H₄: There is a significant relationship between content sharing and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

CONVERSION

Conversion refers to strategies encouraging customers to take specific actions (Mou, 2020). Buffard & Pappasava (2020) found that emotional content may be exploited to increase conversion and engagement rates under the right conditions. Hence, this study aims to determine whether conversion and sales performance correlate significantly.

H₅: There is a significant relationship between conversion and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 illustrates the theoretical framework used in this study. The dependent variable is sales performance. This study determines if five independent variables are significantly related to sales performance.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Research

METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study used the quantitative method to help the researchers gain information and insight into the relationship among the variables and their significance level. This study collected primary data using an online questionnaire distributed to SMEs. Likert scales were used to measure the responses from the participants.

POPULATION AND SAMPLING

The target population of this study is SMEs listed in the IKS.my directory (<https://iks.my/SMEs-directory/>). The SMEs listed in the directory are located across the country, and there are 1,467 SMEs listed in the directory until June 2022. The SMEs listed in this directory are from different categories, not limited to the services sector, and with different sizes.

The researchers chose convenience sampling as a non-probability sampling technique for this study. It provides no basis for calculating the likelihood of each item in the population being contained as a sample. Researchers would use this method to pick anyone they happened to come across. This also implies that the survey will be disseminated to everybody who is conveniently accessible and available at the sampling site. To obtain the necessary information, participants are given questionnaires at random (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

SAMPLING SIZE

The sample size in research is crucial because it can determine the study's outcome. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), too high or too low sampling size will affect the outcome. Based on the Krejcie and Morgan Sampling Size chart (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970), the sample size for the above population size is 302 samples. The researchers managed to get 308 respondents, which is more than the required sample size.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire consists of two sections. The questionnaire begins with Section A, which focuses on the respondent's demographic profile. The respondent's gender, age, residential state, marital status, race, educational background, type of business, and level of involvement in the business are all questions in Section A. The age and education of the participants were determined using an ordinal scale.

Section B contains six subsections that assess the impact of social media as a marketing tool on sales performance. This section used the five-point Likert interval scale, where 1 is assigned to 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 to 'Strongly Agree', consistent with extensively utilized scales (Zikmund et al., 2013). The questions were based on the factors mentioned in the research's independent and dependent variables. Among the factors are brand awareness, engagement, word of mouth, content, sharing, conversion, and sales performance. The items are adopted and adapted from previous studies.

RESULTS

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

From the total of 308 responses, 70.5% were male, with 217 respondents, 48.4% of the age band 30 to 39 years old and 162 Malay respondents involved in this survey and ranked the highest race with 52.6%.

Federal Territory has the highest number of respondents, which were 61 respondents, and it carried a total of 19.8%, and 60.4% of the respondents are business owners of SMEs. The highest number of respondents came from the construction business, with 89 respondents (28.9%) and followed by 65 respondents who came from F&B (21.1%).

TikTok has the greatest number of users, which is 58 people, and represents 18.8%. It was followed by Facebook, which carried 16.2% with 50 respondents. Instagram and WeChat share the same number of users, 48 people, representing 15.6% each. There are 36 users of WhatsApp who, represent 11.7%. LinkedIn came with 23 users, and it, carried 7.5% and followed by 21 users of YouTube with 6.8%. The second lowest social media account is Twitter, with 18 users (5.8%). The lowest social media platform is Snapchat. Only 6 respondents use Snapchat as their platform (1.9%).

RELIABILITY TESTING

Table 1. Reliability Test

Question	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Number of Items
Dependent Variable:		
Sales Performance	.956	4
Independent Variables:		
Brand Awareness	.955	4
Engagement	.951	4
Word-of-mouth	.950	4
Content Sharing	.954	4
Conversion	.946	4

According to Urbach and Ahlemann (2010), indicator reliability is "the degree to which a set of variables or a single variable is consistent in that it proposes to measure". According to Hair et al. (2011), the rule of thumb is to accept a loading value of 0.7 or higher. Upon evaluation, none of the items in this study have a low rating, as shown in Table 1.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table 2. Correlation Analysis results (Dependent variable: Sales Performance)

Variable	Correlation coefficient, r (p-value)
Brand Awareness	0.829** p<0.001
Engagement	0.845** p<0.001
Word-of-mouth	0.833** p<0.001
Content Sharing	0.853** p<0.001
Conversion	0.908** p<0.001

Correlation Analysis is used in this study to determine the strength between the independent variables and the dependent variable. In other words, correlation analysis calculates the change level in one variable due to the change in the other variable. The concept of correlation is limited to indicating the degree of association between variables and does not imply causation. Its primary function is to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between two or more variables (Zikmund et al., 2013). As referred to in Table 2, the study found that sales performance has a strong linear relationship and is significantly correlated with brand awareness (0.829**, p<0.001), engagement (0.845**, p<0.001), word-of-mouth (0.833**, p<0.001), content sharing (0.853**, p<0.001) and conversion (0.908**, p<0.001).

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

According to Zikmund et al. (2013), multiple regression, which measures the linear association between a dependent and independent variable, is the most appropriate method for determining if the developed hypotheses are accurate. The researchers would be able to

identify which factor is more significant in influencing the sales performance of SMEs. Table 3, Table 4, and Table 5 below show the results of the multiple regression analysis.

Table 3. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	0.921 ^a	.849	.846	.30852

R-squared or coefficient of determination is a goodness-of-fit statistical in a regression model that determines the proportion of variance in the dependent variable, which is sales performance that can be explained by the independent variable: brand awareness, engagement, word-of-mouth, content sharing and conversion. From the model summary in Table 3, R Square is .849. It means R-Squared of 84.9% reveals that the regression model explains 84.9% of the variability observed in the target variable. R-squared value $r > 0.7$ is generally considered a strong effect size (Moore & Kirkland, 2007).

Table 4. ANOVA Analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	sig
1	Regression	161.325	5	32.365	338.972	.000
	Residual	28.746	302	.095		
	Total	190.071	307			

The p-value from Table 6 below has shown that $p < 0.05$, which means that the data is likely to occur less than 5% of the time under the null hypothesis. The P-value falls below 0.05, meaning the sample result of this study is statistically significant, and the null hypothesis should be rejected.

Table 5. Regression coefficients results

Independent Variable	Beta	t	SIG
Brand Awareness	0.044	0.731	0.465
Engagement	0.100	1.595	0.112
WOM	0.067	1.303	0.193
Content Sharing	0.238	5.014	0.000
Conversion	0.515	8.036	0.000

The beta values in regression are the estimated coefficients of the explanatory variables indicating a change in response variable caused by a change of respective explanatory variable keeping all the other explanatory variables constant or unchanged. As shown in Table 5, there are 2 significant independent variables to sales performance: a conversion with Beta Value $B = 0.515$, followed by content sharing with $B = 0.238$. The independent variables of engagement, awareness and word of mouth are insignificant to sales performance, with a p-value of more than 0.005.

SUMMARY OF HYPOTHESES

To determine whether the hypothesis is accepted or rejected, the p-value from Table 5 above will be referred. The summary of the hypotheses results is shown in Table 6 below:

Table 6. Hypothesis results

NO	HYPOTHESIS DESCRIPTION	P-Value	RESULT
H ₁	There is a relationship between brand awareness and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia	0.465	P > 0.005 REJECTED
H ₂	There is a relationship between engagement and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia	0.112	P > 0.005 REJECTED
H ₃	There is a relationship between word of mouth and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia	0.193	P > 0.005 REJECTED
H ₄	There is a relationship between content sharing and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia	0.000	P < 0.005 ACCEPTED
H ₅	There is a relationship between conversion and sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia	0.0000	P < 0.005 ACCEPTED

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The hypotheses test results reveal that brand awareness, engagement, and word-of-mouth do not affect sales performance. This result is in opposition to the prior research that brand awareness (Dolega et al., 2021; Marolt et al., 2022; Munir et al., 2021), engagement (Li et al., 2021) and word-of-mouth (Acharya, 2021) has a significant influence on sales performance. This can be explained by the demographic factor of this study. Since many respondents came from manufacturing businesses, they might not place brand awareness, engagement, and word-of-mouth as the factors affecting sales performance since their business is more specialised than consumer-oriented industries. Consequently, manufacturing businesses may believe that traditional marketing methods, such as trade shows or direct sales, are more effective in reaching their target audience than social media marketing (Chirumalla et al., 2018). The result might differ if respondents comprise more consumer-oriented industries such as food and beverage and tourism.

Content sharing, on the other hand, does affect sales performance. Sharing content on social media platforms allows businesses to expand their reach and increase their visibility. The results showed that content sharing indeed has a relationship with sales performance, whereas content sharing increases, so does the sales increase. This finding is consistent with Sufian et al. (2020), which highlights that content sharing is the primary driver of sales performance in online businesses.

This study shows that conversion has a strong relationship with sales performance. The utilization of emotional content has the potential to enhance conversion rates. The findings indicate a positive correlation between conversion and sales performance, whereby an increase in conversion rates is associated with a corresponding increase in sales. The present discovery aligns with the study conducted by Buffard & Papasava (2020), wherein they evaluated the conversion and engagement metrics of 46 distinct social media campaigns. The research demonstrates that under appropriate circumstances, the utilization of emotional content can enhance the rates of conversion. This can improve sales performance.

This study has added to the literature on understanding the effects of social media marketing on the sales performance of SMEs in Malaysia. However, some limitations in this research can be addressed for future studies. Most business owners who responded to this study were from Malaysia's urban, central region. Given that businesses operating in urban areas are well equipped with good internet connections, this could affect the usage of social media marketing in the states from the east coast and from Sabah and Sarawak. Thus, the results from the data cannot be assumed as the results that speak for the entire country.

While social media marketing offers numerous benefits, it also carries the potential for negative consequences for SMEs. Social media's viral nature can amplify both positive and negative content, making it imperative for business proprietors to exercise caution when publishing posts. Negative publicity or viral incidents can spread swiftly through social media, potentially harming the reputation of a business. This emphasizes the need for businesses to carefully consider their content and anticipate potential consequences prior to publication. A solid social media strategy must include monitoring and managing online interactions to mitigate the risks associated with negative exposure.

Indeed, studies investigating the effects of social media marketing on businesses should consider the potential adverse effects. Particularly for SMEs, budget constraints and limited resources can make evaluating the long-term effects of their social media efforts even more important. Such studies could investigate the unique obstacles encountered by SMEs, such as dealing with trolls, extortion attempts, and managing the impact of negative viral content.

Future research could investigate best practices for SMEs to navigate social media marketing challenges, such as content creation guidelines, reputation management, and effective follower engagement. By addressing these concerns, SMEs can maximize their social media marketing efforts and minimize any negative effects on their businesses.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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